

DEVELOPING THE INDIVIDUAL POTENTIAL OF STUDENTS THROUGH MODERN PEDAGOGICAL METHODS

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Abstract. *This article presents ideas and comments on improving the methodological training of future chemistry teachers. Emphasis is placed on memorizing chemical formulas and concepts by using modern pedagogical methods in the educational process.*

Keywords: *chemistry, periodic system, method, traffic light, name, red blood salt, yellow blood salt.*

INTRODUCTION

The processes of globalization in the world community, the development of high technologies and new industries, the digitalization of the economy create the need to prepare future teachers with fundamentally new competencies that meet the requirements of the time. When developing methodological training of future chemistry teachers, it is important to develop skills in working with educational materials, develop the most effective educational technology for this pedagogical process, and test its effectiveness. The use of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process, improving the methodological training of future chemistry teachers for the intellectual development of students, improves the quality and effectiveness of teaching, promotes the formation of independent thinking skills in teachers, increases their enthusiasm and interest in the subject during the study of topics, forms the skills and competencies to consolidate, assimilate knowledge, and freely use it in practice [1].

Chemistry is one of the most difficult subjects to study at school. In the learning process, the student should be the main driving force, the subject of the educational process, that is, all responsibility for reading, assimilation and study should fall on the student. The future teacher, passing on knowledge, should help students acquire it independently. Before each lesson, a novice teacher asks himself the question: "How should I teach?" It is necessary to set a goal and determine specific methods for achieving it. The use of modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods is effective in this. The interactive method serves to activate the knowledge of students and develop their personal qualities by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process.

The teacher not only effectively uses various methods, technologies and programs during the lesson, but also identifies and develops the individual potential of students, works with students individually and in groups. As a result, the teacher, using certain methods, combines knowledge in different fields of science, teaches students to find and solve problems, exercise the right to choose an activity, put forward various assumptions and ideas, analyze, take responsibility for the results of their activities, be able to make decisions independently, identify achievements and shortcomings, look for and find their causes, find and correct errors.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE AND METHODOLOGY

The name "methodology" comes from the word "method" (Greek *methodos* - teaching, path). In the philosophical dictionary, a method is a way to achieve a goal, a certain regulated

activity. The problem of education and teaching methods is not sufficiently developed not only in the methodology and theory of teaching chemistry, but also in didactics. There is no clear definition and generally accepted classification of the concept of "teaching methods".

In didactics, teaching methods are understood as interconnected, regulated ways of activity of students and teachers aimed at achieving educational goals. G.I. Shchukina considers teaching methods to be the most complex component of the learning process, serving a large number of connections and dependencies between them. He divides teaching methods into 4 aspects (gnoseological, logical-content, psychological and pedagogical) and 4 functions (motivational, educational, developmental and educational).

In the methodology of teaching chemistry, there is still no clear definition of the concept of "methods of teaching chemistry". I.N. Borisov calls teaching methods a set of means that a teacher uses to transfer knowledge and skills to students, to form their worldview.

V.P. Gorkunov considered the methodology of teaching chemistry as complex pedagogical knowledge consisting of many components. He identifies 3 most important aspects: cognitive-research (reflecting the spontaneous action of the content of the subject), logical (characterizing the internal side of teaching methods, spontaneous forms of action), organizational (characterizing the internal side of teaching methods, methods of presentation, independent work) [2].

The problem of classifying teaching methods remains difficult to solve. The diversity of classification systems is due to different approaches to their justification.

Chemists-didacticians and methodologists recommend the following as a basis for classifying teaching methods: sources of knowledge (E.A. Goland, S.I. Perovsky, P.I. Gruzdev, S.G. Shapovalenko), didactic goals (M.A. Danilov, M.M. Levina, D.M. Kiryushkin, V.S. Polosin), levels of cognitive activity of students (L.Ya. Lerner, M.N. Skatkin, M.I. Makhmutov, M.I. Lametkin). To classify teaching methods, scientists have developed methods based on sources of knowledge and a logical basis (N.M. Verzhulin, E.P. Brunovey, B.E. Raikov, R.G. Ivanova, M.M. Levina); Binary systems based on knowledge sources and the nature of students' activities (R.G. Ivanova), volumetric schemes based on the level of students' cognitive activity and the logical path of cognition (V.F. Palamarchuk, V.I. Palamarchuk, M.I. Lakhmetkin), and a tetrahedral scheme (S.G. Shapovalenko) are recommended.

Nowadays, an active approach to the classification of teaching methods has been observed. Yu.K. Babansky identifies the following groups of methods:

1. Methods of organizing and implementing educational activities;
2. Methods of motivating and stimulating educational activities;
3. Methods of monitoring the learning process and self-monitoring.

V.P. Garkunov, in his classification of teaching methods, implements structural, functional, and level approaches. He considers methods as functional elements of the learning process and identifies three important criteria as the basis for classification: the dynamic structure of the chemistry learning process, its content, and the interaction of the teacher and students.

Accordingly, V.P. Garkunov identifies 3 groups of teaching methods:

1. General logical
2. General pedagogical
3. Specific (chemical research)

In the system of chemistry teaching methods, R.G. Ivanova identifies general methods (explanation-demonstration, partial research and research), special methods (oral, oral-exhibition, oral-exhibition-practical) and methodological methods. Each of the specific methods has a certain set of methodological techniques. For example, the group of oral methods includes narration,

conversation and independent work with the text; the oral-demonstrative method includes a presentation with a show, a conversation with illustrations, independent work with the text and visual aids. Oral-demonstrative-practical methods include students' work with handouts, chemical experiments, design of devices, modeling, as well as written and graphic work [3].

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

"A good teacher helps to find the truth, a bad one expounds it," emphasizes the German democratic educator Adolf Diesterweg.

Below we will consider the process of acquiring knowledge through the interaction of listening and speaking components, receiving and transmitting information through technological support based on modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods.

Memorizing chemical concepts by associating them with colors

Many people confuse the formula of red potassium salt $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ with the formula of yellow potassium salt $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$. To memorize the formulas, it is useful to pay attention to the words "red" and "yellow", and also to associate the information that a traffic light starts with a red light, then with a yellow light, and that the number 3 in the coefficient of the potassium atom also precedes the number 4.

Another way to remember their reagent properties is to remember that the red color comes first. When adding potassium ferricyanide $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ to solutions containing Fe^{2+} ions, Turnbull's blue forms a precipitate of $Fe_3[Fe(CN)_6]_2$. The number 2 comes first, as does the red color. Knowing that the yellow color comes later, we can recall that potassium ferricyanide $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ forms Prussian blue $Fe_4[Fe(CN)_6]_3$ (a blue precipitate) with the Fe^{3+} ion. Thus, potassium ferricyanide is a reagent for the iron +2 ion, and potassium ferricyanide is a reagent for the iron +3 ion [4].

Memorizing chemical concepts by associating them with names.

This method can be used to reinforce a new topic. The student loves his name very much. That is why he writes his name in a notebook. The text is read out. A sentence beginning with the first letter of the person's name is selected and carefully, without errors, written in the notebook. If a sentence for the first letter cannot be found, there may be a sentence beginning with the next letter. Each student reads his or her essay in turn. For example, Komila: A chemical formula is an expression of the composition of a substance using chemical symbols and, if necessary, indices.

The topic "Periodic Table of Chemical Elements" is studied in the 8th grade. Students write sentences that match their names. Batyrzhon: "All chemical elements are located in the periodic table, divided into periods, rows, and groups." Period: Periods in the periodic table are a horizontal row. "From the periodic table, Irodakhon: "The rows starting with alkali metals and ending with inert gases are called periods." This task is also well suited for group work. They just need to find and write at least 3 sentences.

Expected result:

- the student remembers a sentence that begins with the first letter of his name;
- carefully reads the topic;
- learns to write words correctly and without mistakes when writing in a notebook.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that regular work of future chemistry teachers with students and the correct organization of lessons will increase students' interest in chemistry and develop their independent learning skills. They develop an interest in choosing a career and developing skills.

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